

Communication Pack

D7.2

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Modification Control

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0.2	28.06.2024	Second Draft	Giulia Aprile INRiM

List of contributors

- Giulia Aprile (INRiM)
- Andrea Piazzolla (INRiM)

List of Acronyms

Acronym	Full name
GA	General Assembly
SME	Small-Medium Enterprise

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1. Introduction

1.1 Purpose of this document

This Communication Pack has mainly two functions:

- to provide the **executive guidelines** for using the QUANTIFY brand;
- to give a **selection of valuable tools** to support planning and implementation of project's communication and dissemination goals.

It will be a dynamic document and will be updated as required throughout the project.

2. Brand Identity

This Brand Identity manual provides the executive guidelines for using the QUANTIFY brand, and it constitutes a practical and detailed guide for its implementation and application for an internal and external use.

The following indications intend to ensure the correct use of the corporate identity of QUANTIFY brand.

2.1 The LOGO

THE SIGN

The brand is inspired by the use of a geometric pattern which, like a laser light, intersects in the letter Q of QUANTIFY creating an effect of **interpenetration** and **propagation**, concepts immediately attributable to the scientific themes of the QUANTIFY project.

The logo can be in color or black/white depending on the needs and respecting the proportions and reference spaces.

THE LOGOTYPE

The construction of the “QUANTIFY” logotype is an integral part of the sign and it arises from the customization of a specific font type called “**Resea Bold**” edited in the right proportions in terms of readability and reproducibility, favoring its immediate identification on every support.

The logotype can never be modified or used with other elements.

THE STATEMENT

The statement “**Quantum Enhanced Photonic Integrated Sensors For Metrology**” is a constituent element of the QUANTIFY logo and its use is not permitted in the absence of the QUANTIFY name. There are two different positions of the logo statement. In both cases the individual letters that make up the acronym QUANTIFY are capitalized and bold. A different statement position or size is not envisaged.

DECLINATIONS

There are 3 situations of use of the QUANTIFY Logotype.

Version 1 can be used in all institutional communication materials for the presentation and dissemination of the project where official and complete information is required.

Versions 2 and 3 can be used in all printed and digital communication materials in compliance with the rules of this Brand Identity.

1

2

3

TYPEFACE

The **Resea Bold** font was identified for the QUANTIFY logo while the **Ample Regular/Bold** font was identified for the statement.

It should be noted that a type design intervention was carried out in the QUANTIFY logo on the letter **Q** and the letter **I** to improve its readability and originality.

The image shows the QUANTIFY logo in a large, bold, black sans-serif font. The letter 'Q' is significantly larger than the other letters and has a diagonal line through it. The letter 'I' is also larger than the other letters. Two red circles highlight the 'Q' and 'I' respectively. The logo is set against a white background with a blue border.

Corporate typeface

QUANTIFY

Resea Bold

Aa Bb Cc Dd Ee Ff Gg Hh Ii Jj Kk Ll Mm Nn Oo
Pp Qq Rr Ss Tt Uu Vv Ww Xx Yy Zz

QUantum **Enh**ANCED
Pho**T**onic Integrated Sensors
For Metrolog**Y**

Ample Regular

Aa Bb Cc Dd Ee Ff Gg Hh Ii Jj Kk Ll Mm Nn Oo Pp
Qq Rr Ss Tt Uu Vv Ww Xx Yy Zz

Ample Bold

Aa Bb Cc Dd Ee Ff Gg Hh Ii Jj Kk Ll Mm Nn Oo Pp
Qq Rr Ss Tt Uu Vv Ww Xx Yy Zz

REFERENCE COLORS

Reference colors for the correct use of the QUANTIFY logo in the color version and in the respective conversions for print and web reproduction.

Shade
Orange > Blue

Blue

Orange

Color palette	Pantone	CMYK	RGB	Web
	Blue Pantone 072 C	C 100% M 92% Y 0% K 0%	R 42 G 50 B 137	#2A3289
	Orange Pantone 179 C	C 0% M 75% Y 85% K 0%	R 235 G 92 B 46	#EB5C2E

CLEAR SPACE AREA

In order not to compromise the logo legibility, no external element must invade the clear space area. Its dimensions are relative and are regulated according to the following indications:

BLACK AND WHITE VERSION

Positive and negative black and white version of the Logotype, can be used in all cases where the only printing color is black or where it is necessary to use a full color logo.

APPLICATION ON COLORED BACKGROUNDS

The QUANTIFY logo on light colored backgrounds remains unchanged. In cases where the background color is not compatible with the brand, the negative version must be used. Some allowed applications are reported below.

2.2 Visual Device

The identifying sign of the Q can be used in communication as a graphic element, both in color and in black and white versions.

Its presence must be balanced in space by following the instructions specified below.

A version in a circular space for social use (Avatar) has also been planned.

NOT ALLOWED APPLICATIONS

The QUANTIFY logotype follows very precise structural rules and any other method of use is not permitted. Below are some examples of incorrect use of the Logotype:

TEXTURE

The shaded texture is an integral part of the visual language of QUANTIFY: it contextualizes the logo in a graphic ambient that adapts to the various communication materials becoming a flow of particles that emanate from the letter Q and propagate into the surrounding space.

The shaded texture can exist on colored back- grounds or on photographic images with or without the Logotype, both positive and negative.

3. Corporate Identity

This corporate identity born to create a strong, cohesive, and professional brand identity that can enhance stakeholder engagement and project recognition.

Its overall objectives are:

- ensure that all materials associated with the project have a consistent look and feel, contributing to a unified brand identity. High-quality materials can convey a sense of professionalism and commitment to excellence.
- engage stakeholders visually and physically, making the project more memorable, highlighting its distinctiveness.
- provide a tangible, high-quality medium that reinforces the project's visual and tactile identity.

BUSINESS CARD

The QUANTIFY business card features the negative logo on the front on a background with a shaded texture as per the regulations, while on the back there are the institutional data and names of the contact persons and the European flag (emblem) and funding statement.

LAYNARD + BADGE

LETTERHEAD

The UNI A4 letterhead is set with the brand centered at the top, the full bleed texture on the left side as required by law and the Coordinator’s Institute data in the footer together with the European flag (emblem) and funding statement and the project website. This letterhead aims to give more visibility to the project’s brand, funding statement, and website address when communicating with stakeholders.

CARTBOARD

The cardboard features the institutional gradient on the back with the Q symbol printed in negative. On the front, the complete logo is positioned at the top, and the phrase "With compliments" is placed at the bottom, leaving the central part free for accompanying messages.

This cardboard aims to support communication and dissemination activities, during workshops, conferences, lectures, and research outreach project for high schools.

NOTES

The UNI A4 notes is set with the brand centered at the top, and the website address on the bottom.

The aim of the notes is supporting the QUANTIFY in person events (Kick-off meeting, GA meetings, Schools and workshops) with useful and high-quality materials.

MERCHANDISING

The idea is to apply the QUANTIFY brand to items like a mug or a t-shirt, which can draw attention to the project even after the event where the project is involved or project has concluded. These items will be used as needed, in case events with a large number of participants are organized (International School of Quantum Enhanced Sensors, Outreach events with schools or universities) or if QUANTIFY partners participate in Conferences or Exhibitions that gather the project's main stakeholders.

3.2 Dissemination and Communication supports

The following materials are used by the QUANTIFY Consortium for its planned communication and dissemination activities. All these supports are available within the project SharePoint. The roll-up and the flyer are also available on our website, on the Dissemination page clicking on [Graphic materials](#).

SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCE AND MEETINGS- TEMPLATE FOR ORAL PRESENTATION AND POSTER

EXHIBITIONS, CONFERENCES, TRADE SHOWS, SCHOOLS: ROLL-UP, TECHNICAL SHEET AND FLYER

Two different roll-ups will be designed during the project. The first one is uploaded on the Consortium SharePoint and on our website, on the Dissemination page, clicking on [Graphic materials](#). A first pre-view is available in the following table. The first roll-up aims to give essential information about the project like aim, logo, website (a QR code links to the project website), Consortium partners, European funding statement. The second roll-up is foreseen to give more information regarding the challenging results.

A technical sheet, summarizing the purposes and the scientific objectives of the projects is designed. The first draft is reported in the table below. It is uploaded on the Consortium SharePoint and on our website, on the Dissemination page, clicking on [Graphic materials](#).

The showed roll-up and the technical sheet represent a first draft. Files constantly updated are available on the Consortium SharePoint and on our website, on the Dissemination page, clicking on [Graphic materials](#).

Flyers will be designed if needed. The purpose is giving a quick view of the project and publicize the project results.

ROLL-UP

QUANTIFY
Quantum EnhANced
PhoTonic Integrated Sensors
For Metrology

QUANTIFY aims to develop on-chip next-generation quantum-enhanced optical clocks, magnetometers, and temperature sensors. To achieve this, the project focuses on innovative components and technologies, particularly introducing a photonic integrated squeezed light source to enhance sensor performance beyond classical limits. This technology represents an important step towards realizing a universal quantum computer based on photonics.

Join us in leading the way in photonic quantum sensor technology!

PROJECT ABBREVIATION & TITLE QUANTIFY – Quantum EnhANced PhoTonic Integrated Sensor For Metrology	STARTING DATE 01/01/2024
GRANT 3 ME	DURATION 42 Months
TOTAL BUDGET 4 ME	COORDINATOR Giulia Aprile / INRIM
13 Partners	g.aprile@inrim.it
7 European countries	SA NUMBER 101135931

CALL/TOPIC
Digital and emerging technologies for competitiveness and fit for the Green Deal (HORIZON-CL4-2023-DIGITAL-EMERGING-01)

CONSORTIUM

www.quantify-project.eu

TECHNICAL SHEET

QUANTIFY
Quantum EnhANced
PhoTonic Integrated Sensors
For Metrology

www.quantify-project.eu

QUANTIFY is a Horizon Europe project funded by the European Union, aimed at developing a new generation of quantum-enhanced sensors on a chip: a two-photon optical clock, an optically pumped magnetometer, and an optomechanical thermometer. Additionally, the project will develop a photonic integrated squeezed light source to significantly enhance the performance of the first two sensors.

BACKGROUND
Quantum-enhanced sensors promise to revolutionize measurements by outperforming classical sensors, impacting fundamental research and enabling future enabling technologies and critical sectors such as telecommunications, automation, and healthcare, among others. **phoTonic-based quantum sensors** are a disruptive route to environmental sensing, retaining high precision and accuracy due to the nature of photons and their weak interaction with electromagnetic disturbances.

OBJECTIVE
QUANTIFY will address the "Research and innovation challenges" reported in the Strategic Research Agenda of the Quantum Europe program [1] toward the overall goal of "Harnessing quantum sensing beyond classical capabilities for real-world applications". QUANTIFY's main objective is to **advance photonic quantum-enhanced sensors to a higher level of integration and scalability**. To attain this scope, QUANTIFY will develop the essential building blocks leveraging different photonic integrated platforms, combined by a state-of-the-art hybrid integration technique to bring by key optical and optomechanical functionalities on a single chip, for future chip scale optical clocks, optically pumped magnetometers, and optomechanical temperature sensors.

QUANTUM ENHANCED PHOTONIC INTEGRATED SENSORS

Two-photon optical clock: Hot-vapor based technologies are ideal for accurate frequency standards outside the lab, used in applications like network synchronization, secure communication, GNSS, and space missions. Optical clocks (OC) are emerging as a promising alternative to microwave atomic clocks, offering high performance, lower complexity, and miniaturization potential. QUANTIFY focuses on advancing two-photon optical clocks (TPOCs) by enhancing system miniaturization and exploring quantum-enhanced strategies for better performance. The project will leverage nano-photonic and MEMS processes to manufacture key TPOC components and use squeezed

Optomechanical thermometer: We will demonstrate a single nano-optomechanical system that combines photonic thermometry, mechanical noise thermometry, and quantum thermometry, enabling temperature measurements from μK to 300 K and providing a self-calibrated device. QUANTIFY will develop photonic and photonic crystal cavities to achieve high optical and mechanical Q factors, efficient thermalization, and good opto-mechanical coupling. These optomechanical oscillators (OCs) will be fabricated using a hybrid integration approach, combining quantum photonic and photonic integrated circuit (PIC) technologies, ensuring robustness and enabling on-chip integration. The optical interrogation will be miniaturized using a tapered fiber mode tapered PIC. State-of-the-art LIGO electro-optic modulation will be used to demonstrate thermometry read-out protocols for different temperature ranges, with noise thermometry bridging the gap between photonic and quantum thermometry, providing a consistent measurement across the entire temperature range.

MINIATURIZED SQUEEZED LIGHT SOURCE

The maturing of photonic integrated platforms has improved nonlinear optical processes, enabling on-chip production of quantum states of light, such as entangled photon pairs and squeezed states. The project aims to introduce the first on-chip electrically pumped squeezed light source using advanced heterogeneous photonic integration and micro-wire bonding techniques. This source will enhance the performance of two-photon optical clocks and optically pumped magnetometers. QUANTIFY will also explore the technology's potential in other areas like atomic spectroscopy, quantum imaging, and photonic quantum computation and communication. Honey Labs, a partner of the consortium, will commercialize the on-chip squeezed light source developed in QUANTIFY. Currently, Honey Labs produces squeezed states in bulk crystal cavities and will add the PIC to its product portfolio. Post-project, Honey Labs will further develop the integrated source through self-funded R&D and participate in joint research projects. Their focus will be on European initiatives for quantum photonic computing chips. Honey Labs anticipates applications in sensing, optomechanics, and quantum key distribution. They plan to collaborate with Quik QUANTIFY BV, which needs scalable squeezed light sources for their PIC-based quantum computers. Quik will perform a proof-of-concept to demonstrate the commercial potential and integrate successful devices with their quantum processors. This collaboration is expected to accelerate the commercialization of on-chip squeezed light sources.

FACTSHEET

CALL/TOPIC: Digital and emerging technologies for competitiveness and fit for the Green Deal (HORIZON-CL4-2023-DIGITAL-EMERGING-01)

CO-LEADER: INRIM

DURATION: 42 MONTHS
(01 JANUARY 2024 – 31 JUNE 2027)

EU CONTRIBUTION: 3 ME

TOTAL BUDGET: 4 ME

PROJECT WEBSITE: www.quantify-project.eu

COORDINATOR: 13 PARTNERS & 7 EU COUNTRIES

www.quantify-project.eu

WEBSITE

A dedicated website is being developed, and currently is fully operational:

www.quantify-project.eu

The website is organized in five sections:

- **HOME**: this section offers a general information about the project aim and ambition.
- **ABOUT**: this section offers a general information about the scientific organization of the project. Indeed, there are two sub-sections: Objectives and Work Package.
- **CONSORTIUM**: this section lists the Consortium partners, highlighting the Project Coordinator's Institute and the Involved Started-up. Each logo is linked to the official website of the Partner. A map of the Europe shows where the Partner came from.
- **DISSEMINATION**: this section has five sub-sections: Interviews, Graphic materials (where a digital copy of the developed material will be available), Publications, Public deliverables, and Scientific abstracts.
- **NEWS**: this section has two sub-sections: Events (where all the news about the QUANTIFY Consortium are reported), and Newest Docs and Video (where all the new scientific and dissemination materials and the most recent public deliverables are uploaded. They will remain also on this page for 3 months.).

The footer shows details regarding the project (Programme Call, Type Action, Project Number, EU Contribution, Duration), the European flag (emblem) and funding statement, the Switzerland Statement, the links to the INRiM's Social media channels, a "Contact Us" bottom which offers the users the possibility to address their questions or comments through an email directly to the Coordinator, and the Privacy and the Cookie Policies.

The website also offers a search tool to search for specific information within the webpage.

The QUANTIFY website aims to be a dynamic, with sections updated based on project results and activities to maintain high effectiveness and increase views. The goal is to keep the content relevant and engaging for better communication and dissemination.

SOCIAL MEDIA

INRiM's network of social media channels will be exploited to maximize the dissemination of the project results. Indeed, INRiM's social media channels have a steadily growing number of followers and interactions. For this reason, it seemed like a winning choice to support QUANTIFY's communication plan through these channels.

The social networks we are going to exploit are: [LinkedIn](#), [Facebook](#), [YouTube](#), and [Instagram](#).

The number of followers on 31 December 2023, and on 20 June 2024, are reported below for the involved social media:

LinkedIn: 3717 (4325 on 20 June 2024)

Facebook: 2338 (2534 on 20 June 2024)

Instagram: 398 (535 on 20 June 2024)

YouTube: 406 subscribers

These numbers position QUANTIFY within a consolidated and growing network of stakeholders. In addition, the request for Partners to repost each QUANTIFY content from their social media channels and use specific tags should further increase the visibility of its activities and results.

PRESS RELEASES

Six press releases will be published during the project. As reported in our D7.1 Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan, they will have different purposes and targets audiences. They will be upload on our website, on the Dissemination page, clicking on *Publications*.

VIDEOS

Videos of different lengths and purposes will be published on our website. The first video is already online on our [website](#) and on the [INRiM YouTube Channel](#). It is a four-minute video that presents the project's overall structure and objectives.

WORKSHOPS AND CONFERENCES

Consortium partners will attend workshops, conferences, congresses, exhibitions, and trade shows related to quantum technologies, miniaturized sensors and all the involved scientific areas.

During the project lifetime workshops, and outreach project with schools and universities will be organized with the aim to disseminate project results and approach junior scientists. As a function of project results, as reported within our D7.1 Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan, some other events should be organized at the end of the project, or after, to support the Consortium exploitation strategies: B2B sessions with interested companies and SMEs, round of investors, etc...

QUantum Enh**AN**ced
Pho**T**onic Integrated Sensors
For Metrolog**Y**